

Conductance of Cesium Halides, Rubidium Nitrate and Rubidium Iodide in Diethyleneglycol and Aqueous Diethyleneglycol at 25°

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Conductance measurements on cesium halides, rubidium nitrate and rubidium iodide in diethyleneglycol (DEG) and aqueous diethyleneglycol (aq. DEG, 20% by weight) have been carried out at 25°. Experimental data have been analysed for limiting equivalent conductances at infinite dilution, Δ_{∞} , and Walden products, $\Delta_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$, on the basis of Onsager's equation and Owen's method. Walden products, mobilities and solvation numbers of the single ions in these solutions have been estimated. Results have been further discussed in terms of the ion-solvent interaction.

A substantial body of data on the conductances of ions in many non-aqueous solvents like HMPA^{1,2}, propylene carbonate^{3,4} and trifluoroethanol⁵, sulfolane⁶, DMSO⁷, DMF⁸ and acetone⁹, etc.; and aqueous mixtures of methanol^{10,11}, propylene carbonate¹¹ and ethyleneglycol¹², etc., have recently been reported. But no study on conductance of electrolytes in DEG and its aqueous mixtures is reported in the literature, although DEG has figured in the literature as a solvent in which reaction kinetics has been investigated over a wide range of temperature and a study^{13,14} concerning oxidation-reduction potential of the iodine-iodine system is reported. The present study has, therefore, been carried out to collect the data on conductance of 1:1 electrolytes in DEG, and to get the information regarding ion-solvent interactions from the mobilities and Walden products of the ions in the solvent. The determination of single ion conductivities in non-aqueous solvents has been hampered by experimental difficulties encountered in the application of standard methods of obtaining transport numbers¹⁵. This has, therefore, led to the use of various empirical methods to determine the single ion conductivities, which are based upon the assumption of equal mobilities of ions of certain reference electrolytes such as tetraisoamyl-ammonium tetraisoamyl-boride^{16,17}. But in the present study, Stoke's assumption¹⁸ of relating Walden product, $\Delta_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$, with radii of the halide ions has been employed to estimate the single ion mobilities, Walden products and solvation numbers in diethyleneglycol.

Experimental

Diethyleneglycol (VEB Lab., Germany) was purified by fractional distillation under reduced

pressure. It was further purified by fractional crystallization by partial freezing. The purified diethyleneglycol (DEG) had the following physical constants at 25°: Density, $d_0=1.11478 \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$, viscosity, $\eta_0=0.0174 \text{ N.s.m}^{-2}$, and specific conductance, $\kappa=5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$. The values for the density and specific conductance of the purified sample are in agreement with the literature¹⁹ values within the experimental error. However, the value for the viscosity is markedly low. The extraordinary high value of viscosity reported in the earlier studies¹⁹ may be due to the presence of higher glycols in their sample.

Water used for the preparation of aqueous mixture of diethyleneglycol (20 per cent. by weight) was purified by triple distillation over alkaline KMnO_4 . It had a specific conductance of $1.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S.cm}^{-1}$.

Cesium chloride, bromide and iodide and rubidium nitrate and iodide were of Analar grade and were crystallised from water, dried and stored over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator.

All solutions were made by weight under dry conditions. Conversion between equivalent concentration and molality was obtained from the usual relationship²⁰. Measurements on conductance were carried out in the manner similar to that reported in our earlier publications^{21,22}.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductance values of CsCl , CsBr , CsI , RbNO_3 and RbI in DEG and aq. DEG at 25° are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1 EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF CsCl, CsBr, CsI, RbNO₃ AND RbI IN DEG AND Aq. DEG AT 25°

C × 10 ³ (mol. l ⁻¹)	DEG		Aq. DEG (20%, by weight)	
	Δ _{obs} (S. cm ² .mol ⁻¹)		C × 10 ³ (mol. l ⁻¹)	Δ _{obs} (S. cm ² .mol ⁻¹)
CsCl				
13.72	4.45		46.52	92.64
36.53	4.38		68.57	90.52
54.21	4.32		85.70	88.76
87.67	4.24		108.27	86.50
100.54	4.21		127.56	84.22
			153.53	83.20
CsBr				
40.62	4.00		48.60	90.52
60.21	3.90		60.10	88.72
74.94	3.78		72.50	87.80
97.06	3.70		86.32	86.80
111.32	3.65		108.39	85.00
			135.14	83.40
CsI				
50.16	3.96		30.72	87.80
63.78	3.92		42.66	86.10
75.18	3.87		62.75	84.20
86.43	3.85		72.83	82.25
96.80	3.83		89.24	80.72
			103.85	78.50
			127.84	77.80
RbI				
12.00	3.92		38.56	89.75
28.92	3.84		45.26	87.20
39.71	3.80		63.25	84.68
48.66	3.75		78.24	82.50
59.64	3.70		98.62	80.08
74.79	3.65		125.94	78.64
RbNO₃				
25.74	3.78		40.05	90.88
45.69	3.68		56.11	87.68
56.55	3.62		70.37	82.85
73.38	3.58		83.56	80.00
88.59	3.52		98.67	78.54
104.12	3.48		121.50	76.50

A precise estimate of Δ_o for these electrolytes in DEG and Aq. DEG is obtained by a method proposed by Owen²⁶. This is based on the conductance equation :

$$\Delta = \Delta_o - SC^{\frac{1}{2}} + AC \log C + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where S refers to the limiting Onsager slope, A and B are the constants.

For extrapolation purposes, equation (1) is written as :

$$\frac{\Delta + SC^{\frac{1}{2}} - \Delta_o}{C} = A \log C + B \quad \dots (2)$$

So that when the left-hand side is plotted against log C, a straight line will result if the correct value of Δ_o has been chosen. This choice is made by trial and error. The values of Δ_o for salts in DEG and aq. DEG, which gave the best straight lines according to relation (2), are given in Table 2, along with the values obtained according to Onsager's equations²⁶. Using, Δ_o, as estimated from Owen's method, Walden products, Δ_oη_o, for the electrolytes in DEG and Aq. DEG have also been

estimated and they are included in the Table 2, along with the Δ_o values.

TABLE-2 VALUES OF Δ_o, Δ_oη_o, FOR CsCl, CsBr, CsI, RbI AND RbNO₃ OBTAINED FROM ONSAGER'S AND OWEN'S EQUATIONS IN DEG AND Aq. DEG (20 PER CENT. BY WEIGHT) AT 25°.

Electrolyte	Δ _o (Ons.) (S. cm ² .mol ⁻¹)		Δ _o (Owen) (S. cm ² .mol ⁻¹)		Δ _o η _o (S. mol ⁻¹ .N.S.10 ⁻⁹)
	DEG				
CsCl	4.62		4.55		0.79
CsBr	4.66		4.45		0.77
CsI	4.20		4.30		0.74
RbI	4.15		4.05		0.70
RbNO ₃	4.05		4.15		0.72
Aq. DEG (20 per cent., by weight)					
CsCl	103.00		107.00		1.68
CsBr	100.00		105.00		1.65
CsI	97.50		98.00		1.54
RbI	104.00		103.00		1.62
RbNO ₃	111.60		112.00		1.76

Now according to Walden²⁷, the product, Δ_oη_o, given in the last column of Table 2 should be constant for each salt. But, it is not found to be so in the present study. However, the loss of ionic mobilities does not parallel the change of viscosity of the solvent, and these variations may be related to structural modifications²⁸.

The Walden product may be given by the equation²⁶ (3) :

$$\Delta_o \eta_o = (\lambda_o^+ + \lambda_o^-) \eta_o = \frac{\epsilon F}{6\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r^+} + \frac{1}{r^-} \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

where ε is the charge on the ion, F is the force acting on a particle, r⁺ and r⁻ are the radii of the cation and anion respectively.

Walden products, λ_o⁺η_o and λ_o⁻η_o for the individual ions and hence the single ion mobilities in DEG and Aq. DEG were, therefore estimated by plotting Δ_oη_o versus the inverse of the radii of the halide ions, $\frac{1}{r_-}$. Linear relations were found to exist both

in DEG as well as in Aq. DEG solutions of CsCl, CsBr, and CsI. By extrapolating the straight lines to $\frac{1}{r_-} = 0$, λ_o⁺η_o for the cation (Cs⁺ in the present

case) was estimated in DEG and Aq. DEG from their respective plots. Then on subtracting the value of λ_o⁺η_o for Cs⁺ ion thus estimated from the values of Δ_oη_o for the electrolytes (viz. CsCl, CsBr and CsI, given in Table 2), the values of λ_o⁻η_o for Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ ions in DEG were evaluated. On subtracting Δ_oη_o of RbI from λ_o⁻η_o for I⁻ ion, λ_o⁺η_o for Rb⁺ ion was estimated and subsequently the value of λ_o⁻η_o for NO₃⁻ ion was known. The same procedure was applied to estimate the ionic Walden products in Aq. DEG. And, then on dividing the

respective ionic Walden products by the viscosity of the solvent, mobilities of the each ion, was also estimated in DEG and in Aq. DEG respectively.

The values of $\lambda_0^+\eta_0$ and $\lambda_0^-\eta_0$, alongwith values of λ_0^+ and λ_0^- for Cs^+ , Rb^+ and Cl^- , Br^- , I^- ions in DEG and Aq. DEG respectively are given in Table 3.

TABLE-3 IONIC WALDEN PRODUCTS AND MOBILITIES IN DEG AND Aq. DEG

Ion	$\lambda_0^+\eta_0$	$\lambda_0^-\eta_0$	λ_0^+	λ_0^-
	(S.mol. ⁻¹ , N.S.10 ⁻¹)	(S.mol. ⁻¹ , N.S.10 ⁻²)	(S.cm ² , mol ⁻²)	(S.cm ² , mol ⁻¹)
DEG				
Cs^+	0.52	—	2.99	—
Rb^+	0.48	—	2.76	—
Cl^-	—	0.27	—	1.55
Br^-	—	0.25	—	1.44
I^-	—	0.22	—	1.26
NO_3^-	—	0.24	—	1.38
Aq. DEG (20 PER CENT., BY WEIGHT)				
Cs^+	0.83	—	52.87	—
Rb^+	0.85	—	54.14	—
Cl^-	—	0.85	—	54.14
Br^-	—	0.82	—	52.23
I^-	—	0.71	—	45.22
NO_3^-	—	0.91	—	57.96

Table 3 shows that the limiting equivalent conductances and the Walden products for both the cations (Cs^+ and Rb^+) and all the anions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and NO_3^-) have greater magnitudes in Aq. DEG than in DEG. This may be attributed to the greater structure of DEG-H₂O than DEG. Since the structure breaking ions viz. Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , Rb^+ and Cs^+ will then break more structure in Aq. DEG than in DEG. The resulting decrease in viscosity is greater in the case of Aq. DEG than DEG and, therefore, it could produce the increase in the conductance-solvent viscosity product (i.e., Walden product) for these ions in Aq. DEG over that in DEG. In other words, greater mobilities of the ions in Aq. DEG than in DEG may be interpreted as a measure of lesser ion-solvent interaction in the former case. These conclusions agree with those deduced from greater positive B-values obtained from the viscosity data²⁹ in case of Aq. DEG.

Table 3, therefore, suggests that the following order of ion-solvent interaction exists in DEG :

whereas in Aq. DEG, following is the order of ion-solvent interaction :

Solvation numbers for the ions in DEG were also estimated from their respective mobilities (Table 3) using the Stoke's¹⁸ relation, according to which the ionic solvated volume should be obtained, because of the packing effects from the equation (4) :

$$V_s^0 = 4.35 r_s^3 \quad \dots (4)$$

where V_s^0 is the ionic solvated volume and is expressed in mol/mole and r_s is the radii of the solvated

ions in angstroms. The solvation number, n_s , was obtained from the relationship³⁰ :

$$n_s = \frac{V_s^0}{V_0} \quad \dots (5)$$

where V_0 is the molar volume of the solvent (DEG in the present study). The radii, r_s , of the ions viz., Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , Cs^+ , Rb^+ and NO_3^- ions used to calculate V_s^0 (from equation 5) were taken as the Paulings³¹ radii. The solvation numbers of the ions in DEG thus estimated from equation (5) are given in Table 4.

TABLE-4 SOLVATION NUMBERS OF THE IONS IN DEG FROM THE MOBILITY METHOD

Ion	Solvation Number
	n_s
Cs^+	0.25
Rb^+	0.17
Cl^-	0.31
Br^-	0.39
I^-	0.53
NO_3^-	0.29

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